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OBSERVATIONS ON THE BIOLOGY OF *GEOTROGUS MICHAELIS*
(SPARACIO, 2014) (*Coleoptera Scarabaeidae Melolonthinae*)
FROM NORTH-WESTERN SICILY (ITALY)
AND DESCRIPTION OF THE FEMALE

SUMMARY

In the present paper some observations on the biology of *Geotrogus michaelis* (Sparacio, 2014), an endemic species belonging to the tribe Rhizotrogini from north-western Sicily (Italy), are provided and the female is described for the first time. This species appears to be typically Autumn crepuscular species, with a short phenology between the beginning of November and the first week of December, active during rainy days. The small known range and the numerous environmental disturbances of its habitat, in particular fires, make *G. michaelis* a threatened species for which it is suggested adopting timely conservation measures.

Key words. *Geotrogus michaelis*, Rhizotrogini, endemism, Monte Cofano, threatened species.

RIASSUNTO

Nel presente articolo sono presentate alcune osservazioni sulla biologia di *Geotrogus michaelis* (Sparacio, 2014), specie endemica appartenente alla tribù Rhizotrogini della Sicilia nord-occidentale (Italia); è inoltre descritta la femmina, finora sconosciuta. Questa specie sembra presentare una fenologia tipicamente autunnale e crepuscolare, attiva per un breve periodo tra l'inizio di novembre e la prima settimana di dicembre, in particolare nei giorni piovosi. La localizzazione della specie e i numerosi disturbi ambientali nel suo habitat elettivo, in particolare gli incendi, rendono *G. michaelis* una specie minacciata, per la quale si richiedono urgenti misure di conservazione.

Parole chiave. *Geotrogus michaelis*, Rhizotrogini, specie endemica, Monte Cofano, specie minacciata.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Geotrogus* Guérin-Ménéville, 1842 (*Coleoptera Scarabaeidae*

Melolonthinae Rhizotrogini), a senior synonym of *Pseudoapterogyna* Escalera, 1914 (COCA ABIA, 1995), is almost exclusively distributed in North Africa with a few species found in southern Iberian Peninsula, Sardinia, Capraia Island and Sicily (BARAUD, 1977, 1985, 1992; BALLERIO *et al.*, 2010; CARPANETO *et al.*, 2011; SPARACIO *et al.*, 2024). This genus shows a reduction of membranous wings in the females and sometimes even in the males.

In Sicily five species are recorded: *G. sicelis* Blanchard, 1851, *G. pellegrinensis* Brenske, 1893 and *G. michaelis* (Sparacio, 2014) endemic to north-western Sicily, *G. maraventanoi* (Sparacio, 2018), endemic to Lampedusa and Lampione Islands and *G. euphytus lamantiai* (Sparacio, 2014) endemic to Pantelleria Island. In particular, *G. michaelis* was described from Monte Cofano near Trapani (SPARACIO, 2014) only on male specimens and is presently known only from this locality. Furthermore, the biology of *G. michaelis* is little known and the female is unknown.

Several recent excursions carried out in the type locality of *G. michaelis* allowed us to make some observations on the biology of this species and to find a female, which we describe below.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study area is located near Monte Cofano (Italy, Sicily, Trapani), within the homonymous Riserva Naturale Orientata, at about 250 m above sea level (Fig. 1). The area is intensively grazed and is characterized by meadows with *Ampelodesmos mauritanicus* (Poir.) T. Durand & Schinz, 1894 mixed to garrigue with *Chamaerops humilis* L., 1753 and *Euphorbia dendroides* L., 1753 and rare small spots of Mediterranean maquis with *Quercus ilex* L., 1753. The surveys were conducted from November until the first ten days of December, in a period ranging from November 2014 to November 2024 for a total of 20 field surveys. These were carried out mainly in the afternoon hours and continued until about one hour after dusk. The weather conditions varied with both clear and windless days and moderately rainy days. The searches were mainly carried out by sight, trying to locate males in flight and to follow them in order to intercept the female or by looking for them on the ground or among the bushes with the help of a torch. An active search was also carried out for specimens or larvae under stones or by making small excavations in potentially suitable points.

Light traps were also used consisting of a white sheet placed on the ground and illuminated with a 20 Watt black light lamp (Wood light) and a 10 Watt cold white light lamp (color temperature 6500 degrees Kelvin) pow-

ered by 20,000 mha lithium batteries. At the same time, another self-built light trap was used, based on the model described, among others, by YANG *et al.* (2013), illuminated by a 390-405 nm UV LED and activated by a timer.

Many specimens were observed in flight or walking on the ground, some of these were collected and among these only one female was found and collected. Photos of the habitat, habitus and other morphological characters were taken with a Canon Eos 100D camera with an EF Macro 100mm lens and mounted on a Manfrotto micro-slider movement system. The images were then processed with Combine ZP software and enhanced with Photoshop CS6 software. Measurements were taken (in mm) with a digital calliper or a lens equipped with a millimetric scale.

The systematic approach adopted in the paper follows that provided by BEZD K (2016), CARPANETO *et al.* (2021) and SPARACIO *et al.* (2024).

RESULTS

Description of the female of Geotrogus michaelis (Sparacio, 2014)

Material examined. Italy, Sicily, Monte Cofano, 23.XI.2023, legit/collection C. Muscarella (Palermo, Italy) (1) (Figs. 2, 3).

Description. Length 16.5 mm. Body stout and convex. Reddish-brown, with apex of the tibiae, tarsi and a broad band on the head and pronotum dark; on the sides of pronotum one black spot medially; erect reddish-brown setae are present around the body, longer and denser on the lateral margins of the head and pronotum and on the middle and hind tibiae, short and sparse on the lateral margins of the elytra. Sternum with short and sparse yellowish setation.

Antennae with 9 antennomeres; scape short, distally dilatate, almost as long as 2° and 3° antennomeres together; 2° antennomere very short; club shorter than the 7 previous antennomeres together (club/funicle = 0.63). Clypeus with anterior margin emarginate at middle. Head covered with big deep dense punctures; a slightly raised transverse carina not reaching the sides is present on the middle of clypeus.

Pronotum transverse, sub-hexagonal, 1.6 times wider than long, sides rectilinear at the base, curved and narrowed distally, maximum width towards the middle; posterior angles almost straight; anterior margin sinuate, slightly curved forward, posterior margin projecting backward in the middle with basal bead thin and with sparse little punctures; pronotal surface smooth with medium sized deep dense punctures, irregularly distributed over the entire surface; in the discal area separated by distances similar to to 1-2 times the diameter of a puncture. Surface glabrous, except for long setae along the anterior and the lateral margins, the longest measuring about 1 mm.

Figs. 1-3 — Monte Cofano surroundings (Sicily, Italy) (1); *Geotrogus michaelis* male, Monte Cofano (Sicily, Italy) (2); *Geotrogus michaelis* female, Monte Cofano (Sicily, Italy) (3).

Scutellum glabrous apart from some yellowish setae near the base, wide, subtriangular, with curved sides, 1.45 times wider than long, with deep sparse punctation in the apical half.

Humeral callus weakly pronounced. Elytra broad, dorsally flattened,

wider in the distal half and truncated at the apex, coarsely striated, with medium sized punctures, dense and deep especially at the base and in the 1st interstria; 1st stria raised with small punctures and scattered wrinkles; surface glabrous, except for few very sparse tiny setae on the outer edge towards the apex, the longest measuring about 0.4 mm. Epipleura decreasing in length from humeral area to the half of the elytra, thin and with short setae.

Pygidium with poorly defined shallow sparse punctures on densely micro-reticulated surface. Anterior tibia 3-toothed, proximal tooth weak, medial tooth longer to the apical one. Medial and posterior tibiae with two transversal carinae, the proximal one very weak. Tarsi short, metatarsus ca 0.9 times as long as metatibia. Tarsal claws toothed at base. Metathoracic with very reduced wings (brachypterous species). The total length of the wings is 2.5 mm; the wing/elytron ratio is 0.2 mm., longitudinal veins are present.

Remarks

The description of the female of *G. michaelis* allows us to confirm the reduction of membranous wings for the females, typical of these Rhizotrogini. The notable morphological difference with the males of the same species is also evident (Figs. 2-5).

The female of *G. pellegrinensis*, which lives in the same locality but with a Spring phenology, shows clypeus with anterior margin slightly emarginate at middle, scape longer, shorter pronotum, 1.85 times wider than long, sides regularly narrowed forward, posterior angles protruding, superficial and sparse punctures; scutellum smaller and rounded at the apex, 1.8 times wider than long, elytra narrower towards the apex; anterior tibia 3-toothed with proximal tooth very weak, almost always absent.

Biological observations

In *G. michaelis* the sex ratio observed so far appears strongly unbalanced in favor of males with only one female found in over ten years of research. This greater prevalence of males over females has been observed in several species of beetles (GUÉROUT, 1974; VENARD-COMBES & MARIAU, 1983; DENDI *et al.*, 2021; LUISELLI *et al.*, 2022); among the Melolonthinae and, in particular, among the Sicilian Rhizotrogini it seems to be a common feature (PERNICE, 2002; MUSCARELLA *et al.*, 2022; *pers. obs.*).

In a similar species, such as *G. pellegrinensis*, endemic of western Sicily with Spring phenology, also present on Monte Cofano with a noteworthy population, the observed ratio between males and females is approximately 4:1.

In numerous beetle species, flightlessness is restricted to females, while males are able to flight (ROFF, 1990, 1994; SOUTH *et al.*, 2011; FU *et al.*, 2012).

Figs. 4-6 — *Geotrogus michaelis* female dorsal view, Monte Cofano (Sicily, Italy) (4); hind wing of *Geotrogus michaelis* female (5); hind wing of *Geotrogus michaelis* female detail (6).

Figs. 7-9 — *Geotrogus pellegrinensis* female dorsal view, Golfo Cofano (Sicily, Italy) (7); Hind wing of *Geotrogus pellegrinensis* female (8); *Geotrogus pellegrinensis* female from Golfo Cofano (Sicily, Italy) (9).

Meiopterism in insects usually represents a secondary adaptation, often related to environmental and ethological factors. When only females are flightless, this phenomenon is called sexual pteridomorphism.

In beetles, these two phenomena, pteridomorphism and sex ratio unbalanced towards males, are connected; when the females are not winged/flying, the sex ratio tends to be clearly biased towards males, how does it occur, for example in two other interesting Sicilian endemics, *Pachypus caesus* Erichson, 1840 (Scarabaeidae Pachypodinae) (PINCITORE MAROTT, 1877; ARNONE & SPARACIO, 1990) and *Cebrio (Cebrio) benedicti* Fairmaire, 1849 (Elateridae, Elaterinae, Cebriionini) (LO CASCIO & SPARACIO, 2023).

Sexual pteridomorphism has been attributed to a trade-off between investment in flight structures and reproduction (ZERA & DENNO, 1997; GUERRA, 2011); the flightlessness specific to females may reflect selection for greater allocation of resources towards egg production, whereas males retain flight as it increases the probability of intercepting females (ROFF, 1990).

In these cases, sex-biased dispersal (with males dispersing significantly more than females) leads to a reduction in gene flow in the less dispersing sex. This common phenomenon can influence the likelihood of introgression of maternally versus paternally inherited genes (PETIT & EXCOFFIER, 2009; LUISELLI *et al.*, 2011).

Another hypothesis is that sexual dimorphism in wing development associated with fossorial life habits may serve as an environmental adaptation to increase the chances of survival.

CONSIDERATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

Further research will certainly allow us to better understand the biology of this interesting Sicilian endemic species and to better know also the distribution area, which could be wider than previously known. However, according to our current knowledge, *G. michaelis* seems to be located in an area of a few km², too few to not consider it a species at risk of survival. The most important threat factor is constituted by the summer fires that regularly cross the garrigues of the Reserve. Fire, as widely demonstrated (e.g. PAQUIN & CODERRE, 1997; LISA *et al.*, 2015; MANTONI *et al.*, 2020;) causes a significant medium and long-term impact on the edaphic fauna and on the preimaginal states of many insect species, both directly by causing a high mortality of individuals and indirectly by modifying their habitat.

Some studies (PAUSAS *et al.*, 2018) have also demonstrated a beneficial effect of fire on the populations of some Cetoniinae in Spain such as *Protaetia morio* (Fabricius, 1781) and *P. oblonga* (Gory & Percheron, 1833). As

suggested by PAUSAS *et al.* (2018), these populations have probably survived the fire as eggs or larvae, protected in the soil (endogenous persistence) and benefit from fire because fire disrupts antagonistic interactions with their predators (predation release hypothesis).

Presently, in accordance with our observations in the area concerned, it seems that fire is actually harmful to the populations of *G. michaelis* and to many other species (some of which endemic) that live there, also in relation to the surface layer of soil, often almost in direct contact with the carbonate rock of the substrate. It would therefore be necessary to plan and implement monitoring and protection actions for a species that is as localized as threatened.

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